
**PATTERNS OF SLAVERY AND FREEDOM
IN A CHANGING WORLD
CHRYSOSTOM'S COMMENTARY ON PAUL'S
EPISTLE TO PHILEMON REVISITED⁽¹⁾**

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1. Introduction

The yearning for freedom beats in the heart of every slave. The last letter of Saint Paul in the canon deals with the struggle of a Christian slave, who ran from his master's house, and the role of both the slave's and Philemon's common pastor, who guided them to the belief in the Resurrection of Christ. The text deals with a very delicate issue, especially from the perspective of the Apostle who has accepted both men in the bosom of the Church. The citizens of the Kingdom have a new ethos and it is the role of Saint Paul to instruct the people according to this new vision of the world.

Chrysostom was, above everything, a pastor of souls. This is why he was so sensible to the teaching of this letter and was ready to give an introduction and three exegetical sermons on this "book" of the Bible. The reason why John dedicates three homilies to this work is also mentioned in the introduction to the first homily where he says (rhetorically) that some people in the parish considered the letter to be superfluous because of its topic. Chrysostom reveals also a scientific curiosity to the point of showing interest in every little detail of the apostle's life (cf. Schaff 545). In an attempt to capture the listeners'

1) This article was presented at the SBL International Meeting in Buenos Aires in July 2015, in session 24-10 organized by the research unit on "Bible in Eastern and Oriental Orthodox Traditions".

attention, he first admits that the letter seems to have a trivial topic and then he affirms that it surprises the Christian reader because of its theological deepness.

The present article analyzes a patristic writing from a Biblical perspective. For Biblical scholarship it is always of importance to know how ancient Christian thinkers and teachers used to interact with the text in different contexts and situations. In a first section the issue of social justice in fourth - century Antioch will be briefly dealt with. Then, a first approach to the sermons provides some introductory information that can help to understand the three homilies more thoughtfully. The third part of this article presents a comparison between John's exegetical work and contemporary exegesis. Some questions of method, style and theological reasoning are contrasted and evaluated, taking into consideration the different realities and the wide time span existing between them. Finally in the fourth section the problem of slavery and a theological reflection on it according to the Golden Mouth will be surveyed and assessed.

The patristic text used for this paper is the one published in PG 62:701-720 together with Schaff's translation in his NPNF vol. XIII p. 545-557. For Biblical quotations the New Jerusalem Bible (NJB) as in Bibleworks 9 is used, if not otherwise indicated.

2. Social Injustice in Chrysostom's Antioch

There was a wise man in Antioch called Libanius who was very active in teaching and writing on rhetoric between 354 and 393. He was convinced that Antioch was the most beautiful city in the ancient world and this is why he wrote, among many, the following phrases in his *Oration in Praise of Antioch*:

"Who, seeing the city for the first time, would not think he had come to a festival...? Where else is there such a great stream of pleasures? What occasion for enjoyment is there that we do not have? Have we not mildness of the air, pleasure of

the baths, and brilliance of trade?have we not a spring glistening with flowers, and a summer flashing like lightning with the colors of the fruit trees, making the town a meadow with their scents?What city can we say is worthy to be compared with this?" (Downey 680-81).

It is well known that Libanius had a distinct disciple in his classroom, later called John Chrysostom. However, for this youthful Antiochian heart it was not enough to praise and celebrate the splendor and magnificence of the city. He had a strong prophetic spirit that moved him to accuse what was wrong among his fellow people. Yes, pleasure and beauty were there but there were thousands of slaves serving and being oppressed in the city. He was not able to stay silent. He felt the need to talk and to point fingers. In this context it is worth to show the contrast between Libanius' and the Saint's view of Antioch which he considered a community built on injustice that treated the poor with discrimination, since according to him there were no reasons for there to be a poor person in the city:

"(The poor) are wandering about like dogs in the alleys; they haunt the corners of the streets, they enter into the courtyards of great houses, they cry from their cellars, calling for charity" (Homily on Hebrews 11.3-4; PG 63:92-96)

Further on his sermon, Chrysostom affirms that at the entrance of the great church there was a mass of poor people begging the well-being people entering for prayers:

"When you are weary of praying and do not receive, consider how often you have heard a poor man calling, and have not listened to him... It is not for stretching out your hands that you will be heard. Stretch forth your hands, not to heaven but to the poor."

Christians cannot stay indifferent to social injustice and slavery together with poverty, which were two very serious symptoms of sickness in the ancient Antiochian society. This is why St. John referred

again and again to the necessity of attending the demands of the poor and of showing justice (L. Gnilya 6-9). Of course, the saint's call cannot be understood in the framework of a social revolution because this was not his main goal. For Chrysostom it is important that Christians live according to the principles of the Kingdom and particularly according to the principle of neighborly love: "διὰ τὴν ἀγάπην μᾶλλον παρακαλῶ" (Phil 9).

Historically speaking, a complete commentary in Greek of Paul's Epistle to Philemon came first from the 4th Century Antioch thanks to the works of Chrysostom and Theodore of Mopsuestia (Cf. Stuhlmacher 58). However, the one written by the Golden Mouth had greater influence in the history of interpretation in antiquity, even greater than St. Jerome's commentary in Latin, which was written in that time, as well (PL 26).⁽²⁾ The Biblical scholar P. Stuhlmacher searches for an answer to the reason why both Antiochian exegetes were moved to produce their work. He considers that there were some revolutionary movements among slaves fighting for freedom in a way or another (like for instance the followers of Eustathius of Thessalonica and the Circumcellions, to mention two examples). The Antiochian authors would have been trying to avoid the misuse of the Pauline writings (including Eph 6:5-9 and Col 3:22) as documents that may move to sedition and even violent acts. The Church was growing as a majority religion in that time and the socio-political context was quite instable. People needed guidance according to the teachings of the Lord. This is why St. John is trying to move slaves and slave owners to reconsider their point of view and to behave wisely having always in mind the teachings of the Kingdom of God.

2) See the list of chosen commentaries in Gorday's *Ancient Christian Commentary on Scripture*, p. 309-318.

3. A First Approach to the Sermons

We are in the Antiochian phase of St. John's life, i.e., between 386 and 397, the golden period for his pastoral homilies. According to modern biographical studies, he was 30 year old when he was ordained deacon in 381. Then he received the sacred orders of priesthood by Bishop Flavianus in 386 at the age of 35, and finally in 398 he departed to the capital of the Empire, when he was already 47 years old (Verbeke, 239-40). The collection of commentaries proceeding from his twelve years of preaching in the chief church of the city testifies for the academic discipline and the elucidating knowledge he acquired at the School of Antioch. Most probably the homilies on Philemon were produced in the same time as the ones on Timothy and Titus, following the logic of reading the minor letters of Saint Paul in their canonical order (cf. Quasten).

In his third panegyric (praising) homily to St Paul, Chrysostom sums up his way of understanding the letter to Philemon. He stresses on the Apostle's caring love for anyone in need:

He, who wrote recommending with endeavor and care, would definitely have done a lot more for someone in danger. He also wrote to Philemon, through Onesimus, watching to express all his care and insisting on his requests. Then, who would, in favor of a little fugitive slave, who had stolen his master many things, write a letter without any doubt, and full of affection. Ponder how he was with others. Because only one thing he considered it shameful: to neglect doing something for the sake of saving someone" (Hom. III de laudibus sancti Pauli: PG 50:486).

The series of homilies on Philemon comments on almost every phrase of the epistle and the Saint advances systematically verse by verse after an introductory lecture. All sermons contain at the end a long paraenetic section inspired on both the contents of his commentary

and the pastoral needs of his audience.³⁾ The following table sums up graphically the sections and structure of these homilies:

Section	PG 62	Biblical Text	General Topic	NPNF XIII
Argumentum	701-704	---	An Introduction to the Epistle	545-546
Homily 1	704-708	Phlm 1,1-3	Slaves and Free Men are equal in the Church	547-549
Homily 2	708-714	Phlm 1,4-16	Christians, Free your Slaves!	550-554
Homily 3	714-720	Phlm 1,17-25	Slaves are Brethren in Christ	554-557

This table helps the reader find any reference to text in both languages, Greek and English, aside from showing Chrysostom's main purpose in his homilies: to move his audience to look to their own slaves as brothers and sisters in the Lord and not as servants.

It is notable to observe how Chrysostom in the opening homily raises similar questions to the ones dealt with in modern introductions and tries to give some plausible answers to matters related to the time, place and occasion of this writing, inasmuch as he is interested in stressing on the importance of the letter's contents (PG 62:701-704). In this context Chrysostom, together with many other ancient Christian writers, is setting the guidelines for the principle of giving an introduction before the commentary of a Biblical book.

3) Schaff marks these sections with the term MORAL (cf. p. 548; 552; 556)

4. Modern Exegesis and Chrysostom's commentary

The Characters: The modern critical commentaries have developed during the years several theories about the identity of Philemon, Onesimus and Archippus (a concise summary is available in Fitzmyer, 419-20). Theories have to do with the place of residence, the master to whom Onesimus belonged to, the city where the conversion of Philemon took place. Besides, everyone assumes that Apphia was Philemon's wife. The following table compares some modern opinions with Chrysostom's own point of view:

The Location	Chrysostom	J. Knox	J.A. Fitzmyer	J. Karavidopoulos
Paul's	Rome	Ephesus	Ephesus	Ephesus
Philemon's	Colossae	Laodicea	Colossae	Colossae
Onesimus' Baptism	Rome	Ephesus	Ephesus	Ephesus

Regarding the Apostle's place of prison, Chrysostom represents the traditional interpretation, which was defended even in modern times. In the middle of the last century some Biblical scholars like M. Dibelius and H. Greeven sustained that Paul wrote from his prison in Cesarea, particularly due to the narrative in the Book of Acts where Paul spends several years waiting for his trial and Felix ordered his soldiers to let him be "free from restriction, and that none of his own people should be prevented from seeing to his needs." (Act 24:23). Finally the most spread theory is that Paul wrote from Ephesus, a city that is only 174 km far from Colossae, where Philemon lived (Karavidopoulos, 19). Onesimus ran to Paul while he was in prison in Ephesus, the city where his master had met Paul and accepted the faith some time ago (Karavidopoulos 19; Fitzmyer 419).

According to Chrysostom, Archippus was a friend of Philemon and so is he for most scholars today, as well. In Schaff's translation the Antiochian Preacher also assumes that Archippus was a member of the "Clergy" (547). However, it seems more likely that the term κληρος (*clerus*) has here the sense of the elected ones, i.e., the members of the Church, and does not refer to the Clergy in the modern connotation of this word. J. Knox developed a theory sustaining that Onesimus belonged to Archippus and that Philemon was requested to act as an intermediate between both of them. Fitzmyer in his turn wonders if Archippus was Philemon's son (419), a quite logical assumption in a letter addressed to a man and his household: "The church that meets in your house" (v. 2).

Similar epistles: Modern scholars consult the treasure of ancient writings and look for parallel epistles among them. Most of them mention the two letters written by Pliny the Younger (Epistles 9:21.24). Pliny's arguments for granting freedom to slaves are based on human approaches and on convictions based on stoic strength of mind and dignity. These letters were written by the end of the first century and are related to the region of Bithynia-Pontus (Turkish Anatolia today). St John Chrysostom does not go into such a comparison that might have helped him to compare between Paul's Weltanschauung and a secular one.

The structure: Major modern commentaries distinguish four essential parts in this letter: An opening followed by a thanksgiving; a typical beginning in most Pauline letters. Then, the body of the letter follows with Paul's appeal for Onesimus' sake and finally comes the closing section, which includes some greetings, a final prayer and a blessing (Karavidopoulos; Fitzmyer and Wansik). While Chrysostom does not discuss the letter's outline, he clearly reflects his own point of view on this issue when he chooses the pericopes for each homily. The following table shows the varied forms of segmenting this short but syntactically complex text:

	Chrysostom	J. Gnilka	Karavidopoulos	Fitzmyer	Wansink
Opening	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3
Thanksgiving	4-16	4-7	4-7	4-7	4-7
Appeal		8-16	8-20	8-20	8-20
Epilog	17-25	17-22			
Closing		23-25	21-25	21-25	21-25

Joachim Gnilka in his commentary to Philemon decides to follow the structure based on the principles of ancient rhetoric and this is why we find a text breakdown similar to the one done by Chrysostom. According to Gnilka the letter is divided in five sections: A prescript (1-3); a proem (4-7); an argumentatio (8-16); an epilog (17-22); and naturally a postscript (23-25). Based on Gnilka's structure one can understand Chrysostom's way of choosing the pericopes for these homilies. In the first homily he commented on the letter's opening and presented the general semantic lines of the Biblical text. The second homily deals with both the thanksgiving and the appeal as such. The third and last homily comments on the rhetoric epilog and the letter's postscript.

The narrative behind the letter: Chrysostom does not differ much from the traditional narrative that we find in Ancient commentaries regarding the historical background that caused Paul to write down this missive. Onesimus was a runaway slave and a thief, who had fled from his

master Philemon because he had stolen something from him. Onesimus run to Paul and got baptized by him. Then the Apostle decided to send him back home (Schaff 545). This narrative is essential to interpret the letter in several points. Today, contemporary commentaries are more careful in the reconstruction of this story and base their conclusions on both linguistic and socio-historical data that the Saint didn't have. However, some commentators like Fitzmyer still reconstruct a similar story (cf. 419). On the other hand, Wansink represents those scholars who sustain that Onesimus was sent by Philemon as an assistant to Paul during his imprisonment in Ephesus. While he was serving the Apostle, Onesimus became a Christian and was then able to be a collaborator in the preaching of the Gospel. This would have been the reason why Paul had to ask Philemon's consent to start a new life (Wansink 1234). Contemporary commentaries defend frequently the theory of Onesimus being a debt slave, i.e., someone who fell into bankruptcy or need and paid his debt by serving as a slave (Wansink 1235). Tradition tells that Onesimus became the bishop/overseer (ἐπίσκοπος) of the local Church in Ephesus after Timothy. St Ignatius of Antioch mentions a bishop called Onesimus coming with other Christians to receive him in Ephesus (cf. Ignatius' letter to the Ephesians 1:3 - 6:2).⁽⁴⁾

Useless without Christ: Verse 11 presents an interesting wordplay that has been commented in contemporary works: the name Onesimus (useful or helpful) is set in direct relation to the binomial ἄχρηστος/εὐχρηστος meaning useless/useful. According to Lohse (279), Karavidopoulos (63) and Wansink (1235) in New Testament Greek both terms were homophone to the binomial ἄχριστος / εὐχριστος which mean without Christ/well with Christ. In footnote 6 Lohse gives

4) According to the Orthodox Menaion, the feast of Philemon's family (his wife and Onesimus) is on November 22nd, although his own patronal feast is celebrated on February 15. In the Orthodox liturgy he is considered one of the Seventy Apostles. His kontakion says: "Like a beam of light you shone on the world, illumined by Paul, the all-radiant sun, whose rays enlighten the world. Therefore we honor you, glorious Onesimus." (translation from www.oca.org)

evidence of the use of this wordplay in other Christian writings. With this paronomasia that works particularly well with those who listen to the reading of the letter, St. Paul is able to stress on the useless sense of living as a slave and the great change that Onesimus has experienced when he was called by the Lord to serve the Church and its Gospel. Chrysostom does not go into the analysis of this style figure, perhaps because Greek phonetics in his time did not help or because it was not necessary for the development of his own arguments in the sermon (PG 62:710).

5. Slavery and the Stigmata of Christ

For St. John, slavery is a consequence of sin. Even if one can conclude that his sermons accept the idea that fallen nature gives advantage to the stronger, it is evident in several paragraphs that he was averse to accept slavery as a tolerable social system.⁽⁵⁾ It is very important to understand the context in which Chrysostom spoke, as we mentioned above. Chrysostom's audience is not the only influential religion in the city and they are going through a period of changes and instability (cf. Rustom 265-267; Dassmann 89.108). His words were a true revolution in a society where slavery was well established and considered normal, natural and legal. Therefore, we find here the roots of Christian points of view against this social offense. Chrysostom finds that the letter to Philemon expresses the Christian attitude towards slavery. He was able to see that Paul is trying to change this structure by sending Onesimus back to his master, not anymore as a slave, but as a brother in Christ.

Chrysostom recalls at the beginning of the first Homily a verse from Gal 6:17 "I carry branded on my body **the marks** of Jesus" (τὰ στίγματα

5) We read for instance: "For you know what are the minds of masters towards slaves that have run away... how their anger is increased" (Homily II on v. 9, Schaff 551). Another relevant quotation would be: "We masters may not despair on our servants, nor press too hard on them, but may learn to pardon the offenses of such servants" (Homily II in the paraenetic section, Schaff 552).

τοῦ Ἰησοῦ), and reminds his audience that Paul was a fellow in the chains to Onesimus. Already at the opening of the Letter Paul says that he is “a prisoner of Jesus Christ” (Παῦλος δέσμιος Χριστοῦ Ἰησοῦ; v. 1), and the term prisoner will return in the epistle, in v. 9. Paul shows his pastoral loving-kindness⁽⁶⁾ for Onesimus in making himself similar to the needed one and this in order to rescue a soul from her affliction. The Antiochian Saint says “Nothing is greater than this boast, to be called ‘the stigmatized (στιγματίας) of Christ’, ‘for I bear in my body the marks (τὰ στίγματα) of the Lord Jesus’”. It is worth mentioning that in Eastern Christianity (particularly in Egypt and Syria) these words inspired the practice of tattooing a small and simple cross on the wrist to have the marks of the Lord Jesus Christ on the body and to confess the belonging to one Master. This practice has survived throughout many centuries and conditions, in which confessing the Christian faith openly was a challenge to their own lives. “I have begotten him in my bonds” (v. 10): Paul is in the same condition as Onesimus, they have a common situation that makes them understand each other. They know the suffering of the lack of freedom and of being dependent on the mercy of worldly authorities. Both are considered criminals in a way or another and both await God’s mercy expressed in the acts of human beings. However, both know that their Master is merciful and this is why they do not worry about earthly bonds.

Saint John concludes his second homily saying: “For this also is the glory of a master, to have grateful slaves. And this is the glory of a master, that he should thus love his slaves” (Schaff 554). This phrase sums up the message of his homilies that stress on love and forgiveness. Most of the paraenetic sections in the homilies stress on these two Christian virtues and express John’s way of interpreting the Pauline message: God has forgiven us because he loved us. Therefore, Christians are called to forgive and love their neighbors. The first homily’s moral says: “There

6) A term used 6 times in Schaff’s translation of the homilies and which renders the chief pastoral term in Chrysostom’s homilies called φιλανθρωπία.

is a way to the forgiveness of our sins that needs no labors, nor expense of wealth... We have... only to will" (Schaff 549). In the interpretation of v. 25 in the third homily he deduces: "An excellent thing is mercy! Why hast thou not done it to another? Dost thou wish to be pardoned, when thou offendest?" (Schaff 556). From these examples it is evident that Chrysostom was calling the Christians of Antioch to reconsider their way of treating their own slaves and to forgive them from their debts and consider them brothers and sisters in Christ. Although he does not call for a political abolishment of slavery, he does pull it out of its roots when he asks Christian masters and slaves to love each other as Christ taught. The old and conflictive institution of slavery is redefined by the principle of neighborly love. No doubt that this idea is inspired in Jesus' words: "Be merciful, just as your Father is merciful. Do not judge, and you will not be judged. Do not condemn, and you will not be condemned. Forgive, and you will be forgiven" (Lk 6:36-37 NIV).

6. Conclusions

For the audience of several countries, where oppression and social injustice is on the daily agenda, St. Paul's and Chrysostom's words may sound not firm enough. This is particularly true if we practice an anachronistic reading of these works. However, the contextual reading proposed in this paper shows that both pastors pronounced very courageous standpoints, even when they were exposed to be accused of sedition or illegal behavior in front of the authorities.

When Chrysostom spoke, the political system in the region was changing from the Roman into the Byzantine Era and Christianity was expanding progressively in Antioch. However, it was not easy for Chrysostom to move his audience to stand for the liberation of slaves and to defend the equity of rights for every human being. A task that had been already difficult for the Apostle Paul was still so for Saint John. The very simple Jesuanic principle of choosing the commandment of loving the neighbor as the hermeneutical key to interpret Scriptures

and to practice their message in daily life is still so difficult to perform and exercise that all forms of slavery emerge again and again among countries and societies with Christian background, blighting our global and local society. Once again Christians are bond to engage for freedom and equity wherever their Lord and Master gave them to live and thrive.

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